

The Impacts of Voluntary Information Disclosure on the Fluctuation of Stock Market: Evidence from Vietnam

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Abstract

The study, through the practical data of the factors that influencing the level of information disclosure as well as the impact of this disclosure level on the business operations of listed companies confirms that, by increasing the voluntary disclosure of information, enterprises can reduce cost of capital, increase the market price of the firm value, gain trust, foster absolute peace of mind of a transparent investment environment and create a fair playing field for both domestic and foreign investors. With the above sound foundation, listed firms can enhance enterprise's business scale for their own as well as the overall capital markets and this helps promote the economic development of Vietnam.

Keywords: Annual reports, influential factors, market-to-book value, price volatility, stock market, Vietnam, voluntary disclosure, weighted average cost of capital (WACC).

1- INTRODUCTION

There are numbers of researches which emphasized the importance of disclosure information in published annual reports for accounting and investment. Singhvi and Desai (1971) stated that the quality of corporate disclosure in annual report considerably influences the extent and quality of investment decisions made by investors. According to Financial Accounting Standards Board (FASB) (1980), adequate annual reports should contain useful information to serve for the users in the process of making investment decisions. Chang and Most (1985) determined the annual reports are the vehicle for discharging accountability. Annual reports have an important role in communicating relevant, useful and reliable financial information about a company's financial position, results of its operations and its cash flows to stockholders, creditors and others interested users (Rezaee and Porter, 1993). Moreover, the local accounting profession lays down certain standards of accepted accounting practice and the stock exchange has its own requirements for its listed companies (Firer and Meth, 1986). Vergoossen (1993) saw annual reports as one of the most important sources for gaining insight into the performance of financial information provided by the company itself.

Annual reports are commonly regarded as an important means of acquitting accountability in the corporate and government sectors and often are one of the means by which sectors can improve stakeholders' perceptions of their accountability. Flack and Douglas (2007) reported that annual reports were known as the annual reporting behaviors of a corporation and it has ability to improve the perceptions of accountability among stakeholders and the wider community. In

addition, information disclosure in annual reports is a strategic tool, which can enhance the company's ability in raising capital at the lowest possible cost (Lev, 1992; Healy and Palepu, 2001). Annual reports are used as a medium for communicating both quantitative and qualitative corporate information to shareholders, investors and other users (Al-Shammari, 2008).

Although the annual report is not the unique source of information about the performance of a company, it is considered to be the most important source because of its wide coverage and availability (Hooks et al., 2002). Most companies in every country control and allow the minimum level of information disclosure in annual reports. Therefore, voluntary disclosure information becomes the important supplemental source of information for the shareholders, investors, financial analysts and other users in their co-operation and investment decision.

Nevertheless, Baker and Haslem (1973), Chang et al. (1983), Wallace (1988), Yusoff and Henefaf (1995) and Yuen et al. (2009) have shown that, the annual reports have provided inadequate information to the users. They concluded that the available information on the performance of companies' annual reports is poor and the financial information required by different types of users is different. Buzby (1974) also argued that many items were inadequately disclosed and there has been a gap between the users' needs of information and the actual information supplied by companies' annual reports. Ryan (1990) stated that voluntary disclosure information in annual reports has increased. However, Haw et al. (2000) and Hooks et al. (2002) found that in actuality many annual reports introduce limited amount of information. A lot of voluntary items, which stakeholders believe to be important or even essential,

are not being disclosed in the actual annual reports. Therefore, the agreement between the importance of stakeholders and the actual disclosure level was small and there is an opportunity for expanding the extent and improving the quality of voluntary disclosure information in annual reports of listed companies.

This chapter has involved listening to the needs of voluntary disclosure information of demanders (Financial Analysts) in comparison with the viewpoints of suppliers (Financial Managers). It has also examined the gap between the Financial Analysts' requirements and Financial Managers' viewpoints of information disclosure with the meeting ability of available information in the Vietnamese non-financial listed companies' annual reports.

2. THE ITEMS OF VOLUNTARY DISCLOSURE

Marston and Shrivs (1991) stated that followed Ceft (1961), many studies have measured disclosure quality, but there is no concrete explanation or general guide for the selection of items to measure the extent of voluntary disclosure. Wallace and Naser (1995) defined disclosure as an abstract construct that one could not determine its intensity or quality since it does not possess own inherent characteristics.

Two components were developed to measure the level of voluntary disclosure: (1) establishing an item list of voluntary disclosure; (2) determining the extent of the actual disclosure of these items.

In the first step, we establish a checklist of voluntary disclosure items in the developing countries such as India, South Africa, Nigeria, Mexico, Kuwait, Malaysia, Kenya and China (in Singhvi, 1968; Firer and Meth, 1986; Wallace, 1988; Naser et al., 2002; Chow

relative items ranked by

and Boren, 1987; Hossain et al., 1994; Yusoff and Hanefaf, 1995; Barako et al., 2006 and Yuen et al., 2009). The checklist is referred to voluntary items in the actual annual reports of previous papers. Afterward, all items of the checklist, if similar with the items of the form CBTT-02 have been excluded. CBTT-02 was an annual report form of public-listed company about the mandatory disclosure of information on the security market that had been provided by Vietnam's Ministry of Finance. It was issued together with Circular 38/2007/TT-BTC dated 18/4/2007 of Vietnam's Minister of Finance, and had been revised in 2010 (Circular 09/2010/TT-BTC) - *guide the disclosing information on the securities market.*. These items will be grouped in six categories as follows:

- I. General corporate information
- II. Audit Committee
- III. Financial information
- IV. Forward-looking information
- V. Employee information, social responsibility and environmental policy
- VI. Board structure disclosure

Since this research focuses on voluntary disclosures, the primary list was considered to eliminate all the information that is mandated. All these disclosure items will be checked again to determine whether they are voluntary items or not. The list afterward was sent to some individuals chosen on the basis of their expertise and knowledge of local accounting practices, who work with or are members of institutions that influence corporate financial reporting in Vietnam. The table here is the list of voluntary disclosure items (72 items):

Table 1: List of voluntary disclosure items in Vietnamese listed companies' annual reports

General Corporate Information	
1	General information about the economy
2	Corporate mission statement
3	Brief history of the corporation (the establishment and development)
4	Description of major goods/products
5	Analysis of enterprises' market share
6	Advantages and disadvantages in the development of customers and markets
7	Business environment (economics, politic...)
8	Statement disclosure relating to competitive position in the industry

9	Description of marketing networks for finished goods/products
10	Information of member companies
11	Methods of quality control
12	Company's achieved awards
13	Corporate contribution to the national economy
14	Significant issues during the year

External Audit Committee

15	The role and function of the audit committee
16	Names and qualifications of the members of audit committee
17	Number of members on audit committee
18	Number of committee meetings
19	Attendance at committee meetings
20	Statement of independence
21	Report on completed work

Financial Information

22	Summary of financial data for the last 3 years or over
23	Share price information
24	Supplementary inflation adjusted financial statements
25	Retained profit
26	Bank loan, mortgage and their use
27	Advertising and publicity expenditure
28	Foreign currency fluctuation information during the year

Forward-looking Information

29	Factors that may affect future performance
30	New product/service development
31	Marketing plan, distribution system expanding plan
32	Sale expanding plan
33	Effect of business strategy on future performance
34	Projection of research and development expenditure
35	Project of cash flows
36	Planned advertising and publicity expenditure
37	Earnings per share forecast
38	Future sales forecast
39	Planned capital expenditure
40	Future profit forecast

Employee Information, Social Responsibility and Environmental Policy

41	Total amount of employees for the last two or more years
42	Category of employees by sex
43	Amount of employee remuneration, remuneration policies and bonus
44	Categories of employees trained
45	Policy on employee training
46	Expenses for employee training
47	Reasons for change in employee number
48	Qualification of the accountants
49	Data on workplace accidents
50	Disclosure of welfare policy
51	Redundancy policy
52	Recruitment policy
53	Factors of corporate culture
54	Information about safety policy
55	Cost of safety measures
56	Company's contributions to the community
57	Environment protection programs

Board Structure Disclosure

58	Name, age and address of directors
59	Education and professional qualification of directors
60	Skills and experiences of directors
61	Directors' interests in competing businesses
62	Directors' shareholding in the company and other related interests (e.g. stock options)
63	Number of meetings per year
64	Qualification of the company's secretary
65	Director's analysis of the fee and other benefits disclosure
66	Director's analysis of the remuneration-performance-based compensation
67	Director's analysis of the remuneration-non-performance-based compensation
68	Role and function of the remuneration committee
69	Directors' current accounts/loans to officers
70	Directors' interests in significant contracts
71	A statement of the interests of each director and CEO of the company in equity or debt securities of the company or any associated corporation (class and number of such securities)

3- SAMPLE SELECTION

Similar as Binh (2014), the sample period in this study is only for the year of 2009. In Vietnam’s Stock Market, before the date of 1st January 2009, there were 457 companies, listed on two stock exchanges: Hanoi Stock Market (HNX) and Hochiminh Stock Market (HOSE). The research excluded 150 firms, those newly listed in 2009 (from 1st January to 31st December 2009), since these firms have been listed on the stock exchange for less than one year (Owusu-Anah, 1998). In addition, ten firms of sample were financial sectors (4 commercial banks, 3 investment funds, and 3 insurance firms), so they were also out of the sample. In the total of the rest of 297 non-financial listed companies, there are 98 firms those have not announced annual reports in any kind of mass media (companies’ websites, the two stock

exchanges’ websites or SSC). Since the stock market in Vietnam has not been established so long (from the year 2000), and the legal system and penalties have not been carried out strictly in the disclosure of information, many newly listed firms (have just been listed for one or two years) have not disclosed their annual reports. Little information of financial results or annual reports in accordance with the law is found through the website of State Securities Commission of Vietnam (SSC) (Minh, 2011). A huge number of firms did not prepare annual reports to provide information to external users in their websites. The reasons might be that these companies had not gained good business results, and try to hide them, or they actually have no business activity in the fiscal year (for the newly listed firms). The rest of 199 non-financial listed companies will be investigated as the set of sample firms (with the same sample of Binh, 2012).

Table 2: Sample selection

Listed companies in sample	Total
Total listed companies	457
Deduct:	
Number of companies newly listed from 1 st January 2009 to 31 st December 2009	150
Number of financial listed companies	10
Number of companies that annual reports are not available	98
Sample	199

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Investigate the significant influences of these six disclosure categories on various dependent variables of *Book to Market Price, Stock Price Volatility, Stock Trading Volume and Cost of Capital*. The methodology will be described by following diagrams with:

DSL= Extent of Voluntary disclosure of all non-financial listed companies of 72 voluntary items;

DSL1=Extent of Voluntary disclosure of all non-financial listed companies about General Corporate

DSL= Extent of Voluntary disclosure of all non-financial listed companies of 72 voluntary items;

DSL1=Extent of Voluntary disclosure of all non-financial listed companies about General Corporate

Information (14 Items);

DSL2=Extent of Voluntary disclosure of all non-financial listed companies about Audit Committee (7 Items);

DSL3=Extent of Voluntary disclosure of all non-financial listed companies about Financial Information (7 Items);

DSL4=Extent of Voluntary disclosure of all non-financial listed companies about Forward-looking Information (12 Items);

DSL5=Extent of Voluntary disclosure of all non-financial listed companies about Employee Information, Social Responsibility and Environmental Policy (17 Items);

DSL6=Extent of Voluntary disclosure of all non-financial listed companies about Board Structure Disclosure (15 Items);

MBVALU= Market-to-book value;

PRIVOLA= Stock Price Volatility;

SDLGTRAVO = Standard deviation of log of trading volumes;

WACC= Weighted Average Cost of Capital.

In the sample of 199 companies, three of them have been excluded, since their beta coefficients (β) are

negative in the process of calculating variable of Cost of Capital. The sample is now including 196 non-financial listed firms.

Diagram of methodology:

Equations of Weighted Average Cost of Capital (WACC)

Weighted Average Cost of Capital (WACC) illustrates a calculation of a firm's cost of capital in which each category of capital is proportionately weighted (Bidgoli, 2009). In the case of this sample, since firms use both debt and equity financing, the cost of capital has been weighted to proportion of each (debt and equity) in the firm's capital structure. WACC is calculated by multiplying the cost of each capital component by its proportional weight and then summing:

$$WACC = W_e * R_e + W_d * R_d = E/V * R_e + D/V * R_d * (1 - T_c)$$

where:

W_e = Weight of Equity

W_d = Weight of Debt

R_e = cost of equity

R_d = cost of debt

E = market value of the firm's equity

D = book value of the firm's debt (*since we cannot calculate market value of the firm's debt, in this study, we replace by using book value of the firm's debt*).

$V = E + D$

E/V = percentage of equity financing

D/V = percentage of debt financing

T_c = corporate tax rate (after tax cost of debt is used since interest payments are tax deductible for the firm)

Cost of debt (R_d)

Cost of debt is calculated by using the following equation:

$$R_d = \frac{I_p}{I_{bl}}$$

where:

I_p = Interest payables

I_{bl} = Interest-bearing liabilities

Cost of equity (R_e):

R_e is calculated by using CAPM (capital asset pricing model)

$$R_e = R_f + \beta (R_m - R_f)$$

where:

R_f = the risk free rate (in the year 2009, R_f = Government treasury bonds' rate of return on ten-years = 11.3%/ year) (Cited in:

http://asianbondsonline.adb.org/vietnam/market_summary/vn_market_summary_201103.pdf)

β = the firm's beta

R_m = the return on the market

with:

$$R_m = \frac{P_{Dec} - P_{Jan}}{P_{Jan}}$$

P_{Dec} = Price of the market (VNIndex) on December 31st 2009

P_{Jan} = Price of the market on the first working-day of January 2009 (2nd January 2009)

5- RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

5.1- Descriptive statistics

Table 3 presents names and full meanings of all sample variables. It reported that the level of average voluntary disclosure in the sample companies is at medium level with the mean of 43.36% (ranged from 2.7% to 82.7%). It is much higher than Ferguson et al. (2002) in Hong Kong (13%), Meek et al. (1995) in U.S., U.K. and Continental Europe (18%), Ghazali and Weetman (2006) in Malaysia (31%); a little higher than Hossain and Helmi (2009) in Qatar (37%) and less than Al-Shammari (2008) in Kuwait (46%).

Table 3: Summary of statistics of the variables (N = 196)

Variable	Min	Max	Mean	p50	S.D	N
DSL	0.027	0.827	0.434	0.431	0.152	196
DSL1	0.013	0.204	0.146	0.161	0.048	196
DSL2	0	0.097	0.011	0	0.024	196
DSL3	0	0.089	0.029	0.019	0.025	196
DSL4	0	0.174	0.117	0.127	0.045	196
DSL5	0	0.150	0.038	0.034	0.035	196
DSL6	0	0.154	0.094	0.103	0.034	196
MBVALU	0.151	6.310	1.316	1.110	0.809	196
PRIVOLA	0.237	19.570	6.630	5.360	4.220	196
SDLGTRAVOL	0.306	2.262	0.696	0.598	0.284	196
WACC	0.128	0.673	0.476 ¹	0.481	0.098	196
BETA	0.010	1.420	0.874	0.950	0.310	196
IT1	0	1	0.459	0	0.500	196
IT2	0	1	0.367	0	0.483	196
IT3	0	1	0.174	0	0.380	196

BETA= Beta Coefficient (β)

IT1= Manufacturing industries (dummy variable that takes the value one if the firm belongs to basic industries and zero otherwise);

IT2= Commercial-service industries (dummy variable that takes the value one if the firm belongs to Commercial-service industries and zero otherwise);

IT3= IT-telecommunication (the dummy variable that takes the value one if the firm belongs to IT-Telecommunication and zero otherwise);

The disclosure level of the each category (for each company) has been calculated as follows:

Disclosure score of each category (for each company) (from DSL1 to DSL6) = Total scores of all disclosed items in category

$$= \sum_{i=1}^c A_i$$

where:

i: item has been disclosed in each category of annual reports.

c: total items in each category.

A: Average disclosure score of F.A for each item index.

Since the median of return on market (R_m) = 0.5793, the average firms' Cost of Capital is very high. For each company, the value of DSL (of 72 items) equals to the total value of DSL1, DSL2, DSL3, DSL4, DSL5 and DSL6. Minimum of DSL1 is 0.013 states that the firms in sample disclose at least one of 14 items of *General Corporate Information* group, meanwhile the minimum value of the other DSLs (from DSL2 to DSL5) is 0 (companies do not disclose any items in these groups). It supports the result that the general information of corporation has been most disclosed by Vietnamese listed companies.

The average value of MBVALU of 131.6% (>1) shows that, on average, stocks on the stock exchanges have the market price much higher than the book value, and the investors can believe that companies will have huge gross in the future. Interestingly, the lowest market-to-book ratio is nearly 1/6 (0.151/1), meanwhile the highest market-to-book ratio is 6.310.

The mean of stock price volatility (PRIVOLA) (663%) with a range from 23.7% to 1957% showed that there is a large fluctuation of stock price on the market. SDLGTRAVO is running from 30.6% to 226.2%, with the average value of 69.6% which shows a high volatility of stock trading volume in the stock market. These two variables indicates a high potential DSL2 to DSL5) is 0 (companies do not disclose any items in these groups).

The beta coefficient (β) is an important parameter in the model of capital asset pricing model

development of Vietnam's stock exchange, however it also needs a policy strong enough to stabilize the emerging country's macro economics.

Weighted Average Cost of Capital (WACC) ranges from 12.8% to 67.3% (with an average of 47.6%) which states that almost all Vietnamese listed companies have a high cost of capital. The main reason of this situation is the large value of return on market ($R_m = 0.5793$), that means there is a huge growth of prices on the stock market (showed by VN Index) from the first working-day of January 2009 (2nd) to the last working-day of December 2009 (31st).

The beta coefficient (β) is an important parameter in the model of capital asset pricing model (CAPM). A stock with beta less than 1 shows that the level of stock' change is less than that of market. And conversely, beta greater than 1 indicates that stock prices will change more than the market's fluctuations. For Vietnamese enterprises, beta is ranged from 0.010 to 1.420, with the average value of 0.874 (less than 1) which shows the ability to get a lower rate of return, together with lower potential risks.

Industry types are dummy variables (received the value of 0 or 1). The manufacturing industries have the biggest proportion with the average of 45.9%, the second place is commercial-service industries with 36.7% and the last one is IT-Telecommunication with 17.4%.

For each company, the value of DSL (of 72 items) equals to the total value of DSL1, DSL2, DSL3, DSL4, DSL5 and DSL6. Minimum of DSL1 is 0.013 states that the firms in sample disclose at least one of 14 items of *General Corporate Information* group, meanwhile the minimum value of the other DSLs (from (CAPM). A stock with beta less than 1 shows that the level of stock' change is less than that of market. And conversely, beta greater than 1 indicates that stock prices will change more than the market's fluctuations. For

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a) Model A

Model A is a simple ordinary least square (OLS) regression run with all the included firms in the sample.

b) Model B

Model B is a winsorized regression that aims at “reducing the effect of outliers in the sample” (Yale and Forsythe, 1976). Three-sigma outlier treatment approach has been selected for closer evaluation. By this method, a value is identified as outlier if it lies outside the range from “mean - 3*sigma” to “mean + 3*sigma”, where “3” is an integer and sigma are standard deviations of all independent variables in **Table 13** (except the dummy variables of AUDI, BIG4 and DUAL). This method illustrates 4 significant signs that are similar to Model A, however, the level of significance become more stronger than the level of significance in Model A. In particular, the LSIZE variable, for the first time became positively significant at 0.01 level with voluntary disclosure.

c) Model C

Model C is a rank (OLS) regression “that treats all observations equally in the data set whether it is influential or not” (Owusu-Ansah, 1998). This model has been estimated in several prior studies, such as Land and Lundholm (1993), Wallace et al (1994) and Wallace and Naser (1995). This model shows 4 variables that are positively associated with level of voluntary disclosure: LSIZE, ROA, AUDI and DUAL. Moreover, the explanatory power of Model C is relatively stronger than those of Model A, since “rank regression is considered ‘robust’ in mitigating many of the methodological problems associated with skewed distribution and negative value” (Kane and Meade, 1997).

d) Model D

Model D is also OLS which overcomes the impact of influential observations by removing these observations from the data set (Owusu-Ansah, 1998). By Model D, to ensure that the existence of outliers does not bias the results, we exclude all the observations that include outliers. The outliers have been identified by using similar method in Model B (three-sigma outlier treatment approach). This model excludes 5 influential observations and suggests five variables that have significant effect on level of disclosure.

5. 2- Multiple regressions between level of disclosure of whole sample and of each group (in 6 groups), with control variables and dependent variables of MBVALUE, COST OF CAPITAL, STOCK PRICE VOLATILITY and TRADING VOLUME

Previous empirical studies provided mixed evidence on the association between corporate disclosure

and *Stock Price Volatility*. For instance, Lang and Lundholm (1993) and Leuz and Verrecchia (2000) found a positive relationship between the level of disclosure and firms’ stock volatility for a sample of U.S. firms. These papers stated that, an increasing in disclosure leads to the higher stock return volatility, which can bring profits for a number of short-term investors. However, there are various reasons why information disclosure has negative influence on the stock price volatility. *The first*, Lang and Lundholm (1993) and Bushee and Noe (2000) stated that the increasing of disclosure may neutralize the large impact of information about firms’ performance, thus it makes a reduction for the volatility. *The second*, faster information transparency to public may help reducing information asymmetries in the market, thus enhancing trading volume and bid-ask spreads, and the result is that it would reduce stock-return volatility (Diamond and Verrecchia, 1991; Leuz and Verrecchia, 2000; Mugaloglu and Erdag, 2011). Finally, disclosure may “reduce heterogeneity of beliefs about the true value of the firm”, thus it would make a reduction for “both the volume traded and the volatility of the stock price” (Baumann and Nier, 2004). Lee and Chung (1998) and Bushee and Noe (2000) also found a negative relationship between transparency and volatility of stock returns.

Sengupta (1998), Hail (2002) and Kothari and Short (2003) suggested that voluntary disclosure information is negatively significant with *Cost of Capital*. That means the more information firms disclose, the less cost of capital they have to pay. Wagacha (2001), Healy and Palepu (1993) and Lev (1992) also stated that the purpose of releasing information is reaching cheaper resources of financing and enhancing capital at the lowest possible cost. The investigations of Glisten and Milgrom (1985), Diamond and Verrecchia (1991) and Clarkson et al. (1996) documented a negative relationship between level of disclosure and cost of capital, and tried to explain this disclosure effect in two ways: the enhancement of market liquidity and the reduction of estimation risk. In spite of the difficulty of direct measuring the cost of capital, empirical evidence also found this negative relationship based on the data from several countries, including the U.S. (e.g., Botosan, 1997), Canada (Richardson and Welker, 2001), Germany (Leuz and Verrecchia, 2000), and Switzerland (Hail, 2002) and China (Zhang and Ding, 2006). However, some studies found that this negative relationship holds only under a certain condition (e.g., Botosan, 1997; Richardson and Welker, 2001; Gietzmann and Ireland, 2005), and the cost of capital can even be positively related to the level of quarterly disclosure (Botosan and Plumlee, 2002).

Ratio of market value of equity to book value of equity at the financial year-end is the firm value (Hassan et al., 2009). Barako (2007) found that Kenyan listed companies desired to voluntarily disclose information as a mean of increasing stocks' value. Marston and Polei (2004) also stated that voluntary disclosure will be taken place only if "the perceived benefits exceed the perceived costs" and the best result is, released information does not carry "an adverse signal of the firms to the market" and the positive sign will be released with the published good news (Hassan et al., 2009).

Bessembinder et al. (1996) and Tkac (1999) investigated the impact of the firms' information disclosure on the trading volume. In Holthausen and Verrecchia (1990), the informed effect reflects the extent to which investors become more knowledgeable about firm value at the time of an information release, suggesting an increase in volume and price volatility; while the consensus effect reflects the extent of agreement among investors at the time of an information

release, suggesting a decrease in volume and an increase in price volatility. Based on various surveys of the above prior researches, the impact of levels of disclosure on the firms' Cost of Capital, Market-to-Book value, Stock Price Volatility and Trading Volume has been examined by using the following two regression models:

i) Model 1

$$\text{Dependent variables} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 * \text{DSL} + \epsilon_1$$

ii) Model 2

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Dependent} &= \beta_0 + \beta_1 * \text{DSL}_1 + \beta_2 * \text{DSL}_2 + \\ \text{variables} &\beta_3 * \text{DSL}_3 + \\ &\beta_4 * \text{DSL}_4 + \beta_5 * \text{DSL}_5 + \\ &\beta_6 * \text{DSL}_6 + \epsilon_2 \end{aligned}$$

where:

Dependent variables are *Market-to-Book value, Cost of Capital, Stock Price Volatility* and *Standard deviation of Log of Trading Volume*, respectively.

The relationship between each dependent variable and disclosure level categories will be described in the following sections:

Table 4: Expected signs of regression results (dependent variables are MBVALUE, COST OF CAPITAL, STOCK PRICE VOLATILITY and SDLGTRAVOL respectively)

	MBVALUE	COST OF CAPITAL	STOCK PRICE VOLATILITY	SDLGTRAVOL
DSL, DSL1, DSL2, DSL3, DSL4, DSL 5, DSL6	+	-	+	-

1) Model 1

In **Table 5**, results of Model A illustrate that, for the whole sample companies, the more voluntary information disclosure, the more variability of stock price and the less fluctuation of trading volume are. Nagar et al. (2003) stated that, stock price-based incentives reach for both good news and bad news. Moreover, there is a natural incentive for management to release good news rather than bad news. As mentioned above, if the good news has been disclosed, the more understanding of firms' strengths and advantages will create high liquidity of stocks of these companies, and in the case of emerging market of Vietnam, it suggests an enhancing in volume and price volatility. The high price volatility could bring huge profits for a number of short-term investors. However, the trading volume does not fluctuate significantly. The reason for this situation might be the large total of buying has been met by the large total of selling. Another reason might be that, bad news would make a higher volatility than good news, obviously. In the case of releasing bad news about listed companies or firms' stocks, it would create a powerful wave of selling off those stocks on market. As the result, high selling-demand with the low actual buying will make high volatility on the stock return (decreasing direction) and the low liquidity of trading volume.

The outlier treatments in Model B, C and D illustrate a positive association between level of disclosure and MBVALUE that is not shown in Model A. This reports that the more voluntary information disclosure, the higher value of the market price is. As the result, investors can believe that companies will have huge gains in the future.

Table 5: Regression results of Model 1 (independent variable is DSL; dependent variables are MBVALUE, COST OF CAPITAL, STOCK PRICE VOLATILITY and SDLGTRAVOL, respectively)

Variables	MBVALUE				COST OF CAPITAL				STOCK PRICE VOLATILITY				SDLGTRAVOL			
	Model A	Model B	Model C	Model D	Model A	Model B	Model C	Model D	Model A	Model B	Model C	Model D	Model A	Model B	Model C	Model D
DSL	0.40 (1.26)	0.48* (1.66)	0.16* (2.23)	0.48* (1.66)	0.01 (0.19)	0.01 (0.24)	0.02 (0.26)	0.01 (0.24)	4.60* (2.44)	4.61* (2.45)	0.16** (2.42)	4.61* (2.45)	- 0.25* (-1.79)	- 0.28* (-2.24)	- 0.20** (-2.90)	- 0.28* (-2.24)
Obs	196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196	196
F-value	1.59	2.76	4.96	2.76	0.04	0.06	0.07	0.06	5.97	6.02	5.87	6.02	3.20	5.03	8.40	5.03
Sig. F	0.2088	0.0983	0.0272	0.1	0.8461	0.8129	0.7956	0.81	0.0154	0.0151	0.0164	0.02	0.08	0.03	0.0042	0.03
R-square	0.0056	0.01	0.03	0.01	0.0003	0.0004	0.0004	0.0004	0.0300	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.0414	0.03

Numbers in parentheses represent *t*-values that are adjusted using robust standard errors corrected for clustering at the firm level. *significant at the 10% level, **significant at the 5% level, and***significant at the 1% level. Model A is multiple regression model (OLS). Outliers are treated by following three models: Model B, Model C and Model D. Model B is winsorized method (three-sigma outlier approach), Model C is rank regression method and Model D is excluded method (three-sigma outlier approach).

Model 2

In **Table 6**, results of Model 2 indicate that, there are two dependent variables of *Cost of Capital* and *Standard Deviation of Log of Trading Volumes*, which have been significantly and negatively affected by the level disclosure of *General Corporate Information* and *Forward-looking Information*, respectively. For the investors, it seems that the enhancement of understanding about the business situation of the companies will decrease the firms' *cost of capital*. This result is consistent with Botosan (1997), Sengupta (1998), Botosan and Plumlee (2000), Healy and Palepu (2001), Hail (2002),

Kothari and Short (2003), Clarkson et al. (1996) and Zhang and Ding (2006) who also stated that transparency of information is a means of reducing the cost of capital. In addition, the disclosed information of future expectations is significantly associated with standard deviation of the log of stocks' trading volumes (SDLGTRAVO). That means, the opportunities and risks faced by a firm and future oriented plan of management, which have been supplied by *Forward-looking Information* will enhance the stabilization of stock market's trading volume around the mean value. The future expectation could make an increase in trading volume, but the volatility level is small.

Surprisingly, DSL is positively associated with stock price volatility; meanwhile there is not any detailed DSL category (from DSL1 to DSL6) associated with stock price volatility. The reason here might be that investors and users need the full set of information rather than specific and discrete groups of information serving for decision-making. In addition, the variable of market-to-book value is not significantly associated with level of voluntary disclosure. That means, the firms' value is not affected by voluntary information disclosed by listed firms.

Model B shows the similar negatively significant associations between DSL1 and WACC and between DSL4 and SDLGTRAVO. Moreover, Model C indicates a positive relationship between the disclosure level of general corporate information (DSL1) and *Stock price volatility*. However, Model C illustrates a negative association between DSL4 and

DSL5 and Cost of capital. It seems that the disclosure of such sensitive information takes the exceeded expenses in comparison with profit. Model C and Model D also indicate that the more disclosure of General corporate information will enhance the volatility of stock price. This sign has also been indicated in Model 1 before.

Table 6: Regression results of Model 2

Variables	MBVALUE				COST OF CAPITAL				STOCK PRICE VOLATILITY				SDLGTRAVOL			
	Model A	Model B	Model C	Model D	Model A	Model B	Model C	Model D	Model A	Model B	Model C	Model D	Model A	Model B	Model C	Model D
DSL1	-1.87 (-1.07)	-1.17 (-0.77)	-0.06 (-0.26)	-1.36 (-0.81)	- 0.37** (0.19)	-0.37** (-2.01)	- 0.64** (-2.49)	0.05 (0.11)	10.04 (7.33)	9.97 (1.36)	0.53** 2.19	12.40* 1.70	0.29 (0.48)	0.20 (0.43)	0.02 (0.09)	0.05 (0.11)
DSL2	1.94 (0.58)	1.20 (0.46)	0.08 (1.01)	-0.16 (-0.08)	-0.15 (0.33)	-0.20 (-0.56)	0.09 (1.15)	0.30 (0.29)	6.62 (12.64)	6.17 (0.48)	-0.01 -0.17	0.23 0.02	1.27 (1.33)	0.73 (0.74)	0.03 (0.40)	0.30 (0.29)
DSL3	-1.82 (-0.54)	-2.19 (-0.72)	0.04 (0.34)	-2.00 (-0.58)	-0.06 (0.33)	-0.08 (-0.24)	0.13 (1.29)	0.57 (0.51)	-11.83 (18.11)	-12.37 (-0.68)	-0.12 -1.09	-11.24 -0.63	0.84 (1.1)	0.78 (0.72)	-0.01 (-0.07)	0.57 (0.51)
DSL4	1.23 (0.84)	1.03 (0.75)	0.08 (0.60)	1.04 (0.73)	0.16 (0.19)	0.14 (0.78)	0.26* (1.80)	-0.84* (-1.72)	8.27 (6.89)	8.21 (1.19)	-0.14 (-1.13)	7.63 1.10	-1.02* (0.56)	-0.90* (-1.76)	-0.11 (-0.82)	-0.84* (-1.72)
DSL5	1.42 (0.61)	1.37 (0.61)	0.07 (0.61)	1.05 (0.43)	0.13 (0.4)	0.19 (0.51)	0.25** (2.25)	-0.55 (-0.68)	16.28 (16.45)	17.34 (1.05)	-0.05 (-0.47)	21.90 1.32	-0.92 (0.83)	-0.87 (-1.05)	-0.10 (-1.02)	-0.55 (-0.68)
DSL6	2.71 (1.27)	2.93 (1.46)	0.08 (0.58)	3.25 (1.57)	0.34 (0.25)	0.32 (1.32)	0.20 (1.53)	-0.87 (-1.25)	-8.51 (13.32)	-8.72 (-0.65)	-0.17 (-1.28)	-9.34 -0.70	-0.56 (0.71)	-0.63 (-0.89)	-0.09 (-0.73)	-0.87 (-1.25)
Obs	196	196	196	186	196	196	196	188	196	196	196	188	196	196	196	188
F-value	0.92	1.07			0.93	0.95	1.45	2.06	1.44	1.46	1.59	2.04	2.03	2.04	1.93	2.06
Sig. F	0.48	0.38	0.41	0.55	0.48	0.46	0.20	0.06	0.20	0.19	0.15	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.08	0.06
R-square	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.05	0.06	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.06	0.06	0.05	0.06	0.06

Independent variables are DSL categories from DSL1 to DSL6; dependent variables are MBVALUE, STOCK PRICE VOLATILITY, SDLGTRAVOL and COST OF CAPITAL, respectively. Numbers in parentheses represent *t*-values that are adjusted using robust standard errors corrected for clustering at the firm level. *significant at the 10% level, **significant at the 5% level, and***significant at the 1% level. Model A is multiple regression model (OLS). Outliers are treated by following three models: Model B, Model C and Model D. Model B is winsorized method (three-sigma outlier approach), Model C is rank regression method and Model D is excluded method (three-sigma outlier approach).

2) Robustness check

For robustness check, we include control variables in Model 1 and Model 2 to examine the relationship between disclosure categories and each dependent variables of *Cost of Capital*, *Market-to-Book value*, *Stock Price Volatility* and *Standard deviation of Log of Trading Volume*. In particularly, the control variables have been used as followed:

Table 7: Control variables that have been used in robustness checks

	MBVALUE	WACC	PRIVOLA	SDLGTRAVO
Control variables included	<i>Profitability (ROA)</i>	<i>Leverage (LEV)</i>	<i>Profitability (ROA)</i>	<i>Institutional ownership (INSTI)</i>
Prior studies	Berk (1995)	Francis et al. (2005)	Moeinadin et al. (2011)	Bessembinder et al. (1996) and Tkac (1999)
Signs in prior studies	+	+	+	+

In **Table 8**, for robustness check of Model 1, the dependent variables of *Market-to-Book value*, *Cost of Capital*, *Stock Price Volatility* and *Standard deviation of Log of Trading Volume* are all positively associated with control variables and consistent with prior studies. Moreover, although MBVALUE drops its significant relationship with level of disclosure, other coefficients do not change its sign when the control variables are added. Our main results are robust. Similarly, the results in Model 2 are also robust since control variables are all positively associated with dependent variables as prior studies and similar signs have been found in the relationship between DSL1 and *Stock Price Volatility* and *Standard deviation of Log of Trading Volume*.

Table 8: Robustness check for Model 1

Variables	MBVALUE	COST OF CAPITAL	STOCK PRICE VOLATILITY	SDLGTRAVOL
DSL	0.1204 (0.37)	0.0017 (0.03)	3.1469* (1.69)	-0.2503* (-1.80)
LEV		0.0132** (2.62)		
ROA	3.4083** (2.28)		17.8081*** (2.70)	
INSTI				0.1727** (2.01)
Obs.	196	196	196	196
F-value	3.73	3.50	8.33	3.09
Sig. F	0.0259	0.0321	0.0003	0.0476
R-square	0.1458	0.1419	0.1674	0.0375

Independent variable is DSL; dependent variables are MBVALUE, COST OF CAPITAL, STOCK PRICE VOLATILITY and SDLGTRAVOL, respectively. Numbers in parentheses represent *t*-values that are adjusted using robust standard errors corrected for clustering at the firm level. *significant at the 10% level, **significant at the 5% level, and***significant at the 1% level. Model A is multiple regression model (OLS). Outliers are treated by following three models: Model B, Model C and Model D. Model B is winsorized method, Model C is rank regression method and Model D is excluded method.

Table 9: Robustness check for Model 2

Variables	MBVALUE	COST OF CAPITAL	STOCK PRICE VOLATILITY	SDLGTRAVOL
DSL1	-1.7221 (-1.06)	-0.3435** (-2.06)	10.8355* (1.69)	0.2529 (0.52)
DSL2	1.4891 (0.46)	-0.1033 (-0.34)	4.1927 (0.35)	1.3301 (1.01)
DSL3	-3.0291 (-1.06)	-0.1038 (-0.34)	-18.3580 (-1.21)	0.7408 (0.69)
DSL4	0.1083 (0.07)	0.2330 (1.37)	2.2047 (0.36)	-0.9232 (-1.64)
DSL5	2.4888 (1.15)	-0.0119 (-0.03)	22.0477 (1.57)	-0.9218 (-1.16)
DSL6	2.1769 (1.10)	0.3242 (1.45)	-11.4022 (-0.94)	-0.5644 (-0.81)
LEV		0.0132*** (2.59)		
ROA	3.4271** (2.24)		18.4717*** (2.74)	
INSTI				0.1663** (1.98)
Obs.	196	196	196	196
F-value	1.66	2.10	3.35	2.30
Sig. F	0.0222	0.0460	0.0022	0.0285
R-square	0.1621	0.1684	0.1871	0.0714

Independent variables are DSL categories from DSL1 to DSL6; dependent variables are MBVALUE, STOCK PRICE VOLATILITY, SDLGTRAVOL and COST OF CAPITAL, respectively. Numbers in parentheses represent *t*-values that are adjusted using robust standard errors corrected for clustering at the firm level. *significant at the 10% level, **significant at the 5% level, and***significant at the 1% level. Model A is multiple regression model (OLS). Outliers are treated by following three models: Model B, Model C and Model D. Model B is winsorized method (three-sigma outlier approach), Model C is rank regression method and Model D is excluded method (three-sigma outlier approach).

5- CONCLUSIONS

This study is one of the first papers that examine the level of voluntary disclosure among Vietnamese non-financial listed companies. It investigates the requirements of information in the annual reports of Vietnam's Financial Analysts, illustrates the viewpoints

of Financial Managers and measures the actual voluntary level in the Vietnamese Corporations' annual reports. It also determines the relationship between firms' characteristics, ownership structure, corporate governance structure and the extent of voluntary disclosure in the annual reports of 199 Vietnamese listed companies in the year ending 31st December 2009.

The important finding of this paper is, the more voluntary disclosure, especially General Corporate Information and Forward-looking Information, the less cost of capital that firms have to pay, the more variability of the stock returns and the less volatility of trading volume on Vietnamese stock market. This result indicates the fact that a good understanding of the companies' business situation, historical establishment and bright expectations of near future developments will reduce the firms' capital cost and fluctuation of trading volume, therefore managements of Vietnamese listed firms should *disclose as much as possible* in *General and Forward-looking Information* in annual reports. While it does not cost firms a lot, it can make a great

effect in reducing companies' expenses and stabilizing the firms' trading volume in the context of high stock price volatility. These results are associated with other studies in both developed countries like U.S. (Botosan, 1997; Botosan and Plumlee, 2000) and developing country like China (Zhang and Ding, 2006), which provide a negative relation between cost of equity capital and extent of their voluntary disclosures. Standing on the level of the sample listed companies, releasing information would help investors to enhance their knowledge of strengths and weakness of firms, thus have high confidence in making decision of buying or selling stocks. As the result, although the stock price fluctuates, the trading volume could maintain more stable. For the whole company sample, the higher voluntary information disclosure, the higher variability of the stock returns and the higher stable trading volume are. These findings are meaningful for management in considering what kinds of and to what extent information should be released in the process of preparing corporate annual reports.

In addition, it seems that the enhancement of understanding about the business situation of the companies will decrease the firms' cost of capital. This result is consistent with series of other studies that also stated that transparency of information is a means of reducing the cost of capital. Moreover, the disclosed information of future expectations is significantly associated with standard deviation of the log of stocks' trading volumes (SDLGTRAVO). That means, the opportunities and risks faced by a firm and future oriented plan of management, which have been supplied by *Forward-looking Information* will enhance the stabilization of stock market's trading volume around the mean value. The future expectation could make an increase in trading volume, but the volatility level is small.

For the firms' management, this study recommends that, on one hand they need to strengthen supervision and monitoring the performance of information disclosure of listed companies, on the other hand they need to improve the quality, content and diversify means of information disclosure under the motto: full, timely, accurate and accessible. What is more, the state should have strict sanctions in forcing firms to stop listing for the firms that do not publish or not provide complete, timely information or deliberately conceal information detrimental to investors.

This paper, through the practical data of the factors that influencing the level of information disclosure as well as the impact of this disclosure level on the business operations of listed companies confirms that, by increasing the voluntary disclosure of information, enterprises can reduce cost of capital,

increase the market price of the firm value, gain trust, foster absolute peace of mind of a transparent investment environment and create a fair playing field for both domestic and foreign investors. With the above sound foundation, listed firms can enhance enterprise's business scale for their own as well as the overall capital markets and this helps promote the economic development of Vietnam.

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